

Sound Measurements from Workplace Incivility Scale

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ABSTRACT

Measurement of Workplace Incivility (WI) by popular Workplace incivility scale (WIS) suffers from limitations including methodological limitations. The paper suggests transformation of item wise WIS scores (X_i) to normally distributed scores (P_i) in the range 1 to 100 and scale score (WSI_i) as sum of his/her P_i s enabling meaningful arithmetic aggregation. Normally distributed monotonic WSI -scores satisfy the basic assumption of parametric statistical techniques and facilitate better comparisons, assessment of progress over time, efficiency of classification by within-cluster and between-cluster distances and better computation of psychometric qualities in terms of theoretically defined reliability, factorial validity, etc. Empirical relationship between WIS -scores and factors contributing to workplace incivility can be found. Moreover, for assessment of impacts of WI, the proposed WIS -scores may be regressed on decreased level of job satisfaction, impaired performance, lower productivity, less commitment to work, lack of loyalty to the organization, decreased satisfaction with managers and colleagues, a sense of injustice and conflict between work and family and increased absenteeism and turnover intentions. Future studies suggested.

KEYWORDS: Workplace Incivility, Arithmetic aggregation, Normal distribution, Progress path, Theoretical reliability, Factorial validity

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INTRODUCTION

Workplace incivility (WI) in the workplace is characterized by disrespectful or rude behavior, resulting in violation of perceived norms of mutual respect in the workplace, bullying, etc. (Anderson & Pearson, 1999). It may be defined as low-intensity deviant behavior with ambiguous intent to harm the target in violation of workplace norms for mutual respect. (Odufuwa and Taiwo, 2024). Despite conceptual and empirical overlaps among incivility, ostracism, bullying, and abusive supervision, incivility involving low-intensity deviant acts (unlike higher intensity of workplace bullying), no physical intensity (unlike physically abusive supervision), ambiguous intent (unlike workplace bullying and supervision) is considered distinct (Yao et al., 2021). Regarding prevalence, Porath and Pearson (2013) found that workplace incivility was experienced by the employees in the United States at least once in their work life was 98% including half of them experiencing WI on a weekly basis. Bilal et al. (2024) found empirically that routine work instability positively affects frustration and act as a hindrance to perform duties in professional fashion. Workplace incivility was found to be more likely when team has high levels of interpersonal conflicts (Roberts, 2013) and less likely when team works with supervisors' supports (Holm et al. 2019)

The commonly used scale for measuring incivility is the 4-point Workplace Incivility Scale (WIS) containing 7-items, to assess WI experience like rude, condescending, and ostracizing experiences on the job. Here, respondents indicate frequencies of their experience during last five years of various uncivil behaviors, including use of unprofessional terms, being put down or being ignored or excluded from professional camaraderie (Cortina et al., 2001). Responses are scored as 4 for Strongly Agree, 3: Agree, 2: Disagree and 1: Strongly Disagree. The WIS was revised to 12-item version in 2013. Both versions scored as sum or mean of all items were validated based on hostile interpersonal behavior by supervisors and juniors (Cortina et al. 2001; Cortina et al. 2013). Incivility can be seen from the perspective of the victim and also from the instigator. Incivility results in stress to the victims and also to those who engage in uncivil behaviors and is associated with an array of job attitudes, job satisfaction, burnout, absenteeism, organizational commitment, intention to leave, etc. (Han et al., 2021; Park & Martinez, 2021). The victims are more likely to have

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low self-esteem (Yao et al., 2021). Workplace incivility from the angle of instigators may help to reduce if not prevent incivility at workplace (Jex et al. 2010; Meier and Semmer, 2013).

Personality types or traits differ for employees who engage in uncivil behaviors and people who are less likely to be uncivil toward others (Park & Martinez, 2021). Uncivil actions may create a snowball effect and affect the organization climate since the victims of incivility may need to balance and act uncivil fashion and can become instigators. Employees receiving incivility are more likely to enact incivility toward their coworkers and experience emotional exhaustion (Yun et al. 2024). Porath & Pearson (2013) observed empirically that prevalence of large percentage of workers experience incivility forced the management of Fortune 100 companies to spend about 13% of their time on fallout from the incidences of incivility.

However, the WIS suffers from methodological limitations. For example, the boundary points for classification (cut-off scores) of WIS are not unanimously agreed and efficiency of classification is unknown. It fails to differentiate uncivil behaviors coming from the different elements of the organization. It does not consider the cultural differences and ignores uncivil behaviors typical of specific countries (Handoyo et al. 2018). Norms of respectful or disrespectful behaviors do differ among cultures (Montgomery et al. 2004). Occupation-specific WI measures developed like Nursing Incivility Scale (Guidroz et al. 2010), incivility from customers scale (Wilson and Holmval, 2013).

Methodological limitations of ordinal WIS scale are:

- Addition is not meaningful for ordinal data generated by responses of the subjects taking the WIS since equidistant property is not satisfied. Latent distance between *Agree* (scored as 3) and *Disagree* (scored as 2) is not equal to the latent distance between *Strongly Agree* (scored as 4) and *Agree* (Jamieson, 2004). Distance between observed frequencies of successive response-categories is not a good measure of latent distance between successive response-categories.
- For ordinal scale, $\bar{X} > \bar{Y}$ or $\bar{X} < \bar{Y}$ is meaningless (Hand, 1996).
- Non-admissibility of meaningful addition distorts standard deviation (SD), correlation, Cronbach α for test reliability, etc.
- Equal importance to the items for summative WIS score ignores different factor loadings and different contributions of items to total score, different item-total correlations, etc. (Parkin et al. 2010).
- Unknown distributions of item scores and scale scores may give distorted results of testing equality of mean WIS for two groups and techniques like PCA, FA, SEM, etc. which assume normally distributed scores.
- It is problematic to find joint distribution of scale scores without knowledge of distributions of item scores. One solution is to convert scores of each item to follow normal distribution where parameters of the distribution can be obtained from the data (Chakrabarty et al. 2022)
- From the angle of distribution, $Z = X + Y$ demands knowledge of distributions of X and Y with known or estimated probability density function f_x and f_y respectively and finding f_z so that $f_z(z) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_x(x)f_y(z-x) dx$ for continuous variables. Similar convolution of discrete variables can be defined (Chakrabarty, 2023). Methodological limitations and empirical inconsistencies of arithmetic aggregations have been discussed by various researchers (Barnat et al. 2019; Stoet and Geary, 2015; Hsu et al. 2016). For arithmetic aggregation, indicator scores may be converted to continuous monotonic scores following Normal Distribution (Chakrabarty, 2022).

The paper suggests transfer of item wise WIS scores (X_i) to normally distributed scores (P_i) and scale score of i -th subject (WSI_i) as sum of his/her P_i s enabling meaningful arithmetic aggregation. Normally distributed scores satisfy the basic assumption of parametric statistical techniques and facilitate better comparisons, computation of psychometric qualities.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Uncivil acts by may create a snowball effect and can affect the whole organization since the victims may feel need to counter the uncivilly acts faced by them. Higher levels of workplace incivility contribute to higher burnout (Fida et al. 2018).

High factor loadings of each of the seven items in WIS (minimum: 0.58) indicating moderate to high correlation between the item and the factor which tend to suggest unidimensionality of the scale (Cortina et al. 2001). Details are shown below:

Item	Factor loading
Have you been in a situation in the last five years where any of your superiors or coworkers:	
Put you down or was condescending to you?	0.84
Paid little attention to your statement or showed little interest in your opinion?	0.79
Made demeaning or derogatory remarks about you?	0.74
Addressed you in unprofessional terms, either publicly or privately?	0.73
Ignored or excluded you from professional camaraderie?	0.72
Doubted your judgment on a matter over which you have responsibility?	0.71
Made unwanted attempts to draw you into a discussion of personal matters?	0.58

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Sample based factor loadings of items of WIS differ across investigations. [Shade et al. \(2014\)](#) found factor loading for the 7-th item of WIS was 0.71 in the Swedish translation. The

7-th item of WIS with lowest factor loading was not favoured by researchers like [Kabat-Farr et al. \(2018\)](#) who came out with 6-item WIS measure, dropping the 7-th item.

Single dimension of WIS does not go hand in hand with perceptions of incivility in workplace. For example, supervisor incivility and co-worker incivility may have different behavioral forms in different dimensions depending on cultural differences, educational levels, etc. In addition, the list of uncivil behaviors in WIS appears to be incomplete and cannot cover ever changing ways of showing disrespect to others including nonverbal behaviors like excluding others, glaring or ignoring colleagues ([Lim et al., 2008](#)). However, [Smidt et al. \(2016\)](#) found three factor model best fitted the WIS data with three sources of workplace incivility viz. supervisor, colleague and instigated.

Multidimensional incivility was assessed using different scales like Uncivil Workplace Behavior Questionnaire (UWBQ) with 17 items and four factors: hostility, privacy invasion, exclusionary behavior, and gossiping ([Martin & Hine, 2005](#)) focusing on the past year only; Straightforward Incivility Scale (SIS) ([Leiter & Day, 2013](#)) comprising of three subscales (supervisor, coworker, and instigated incivility) that assess the frequency of incivility experienced from one's supervisor, co-workers, and physicians over the past 6 months. Each subscale contains five number of 7-point items from 0 (never) to 6 (daily). Here, subjects to indicate frequency of people speaking or behaving rudely, where definition or concept of rude behaviours is left to the subjects. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) resulted in better fit of three-factor structure of Italian version of SIS ([Portoghese et al. 2015](#)). However, use of modification indices to improve the overall model fit is not beyond criticism. [Portoghese et al. \(2015\)](#) suggested finding factor structure of the SIS with different data. Among the various methods to assess dimensionality, straightforward answer is to find number of independent factors (eigenvalue >1) by Principal component analysis (PCA).

Regardless of scale to assess incivility, focusing mainly on the perspective of targets and less emphasis on instigator's perspective, [Park and Martinez \(2021\)](#) suggested *risk factors* associated with a higher propensity of incivility instigation and *preventative factors* associated with lower propensity.

Validity:

Convergent validity of summated scores of WIS was obtained as correlation with positively skewed two factor PIFT scale, consisting of 18-items on two subscales: Supervisor subscale with 14 items and Coworker subscale with 4 items where each item was scored as 3 for positive response, 1 for negative response and 2 for choosing the response with "?". Dissimilarity of factor structure of WIS and chosen criterion scale is a major limitation of such validity. Question may arise whether the computed validity is for WIS or for the criterion scale. Validity of WIS as correlation with bullying and poor health-related quality of life (HRQoL) ([Cortina et al., 2001](#); [Schad et al., 2014](#)) does not appear to be meaningful since the concept of workplace incivility is different from concepts of workplace bullying or HRQoL.

Reliability:

Cronbach's alpha is commonly used to find reliability of WIS or SIS. For the Italian version of SIS, [Portoghese et al. \(2015\)](#) found Cronbach's alpha exceeded 0.80 for each sub-scale and the SIS. However, the authors did not consider (i) relationship of reliability of the entire scale with reliabilities of the sub-scales and (ii) alpha does not work well for a multidimensional scale because of violation of tau equivalence.

Other limitations:

- Data on workplace incivility are self-reported which run the risk of response bias ([Antonakis, et al. 2010](#)).
- Some WIS items lack conceptual precision. For example, putting down a co-worker is an overt, active, and direct act of disrespect and not a low intensity act.
- Non-probability sampling method like convenient sampling usually employed may not help generalization of the results with confidence.
- Cross-sectional data limits the possibility of effects with time lags.
- Longitudinal study with at least four time points testing the posited model would strengthen the results and provide additional support for our conclusions.
- Relation between workplace incivility and employee's experience of stress, recovery, value congruence and the intention to quit through theories of Risk Management Model and Dys-empowerment theory are only partially explained ([Jiménez et al. 2015](#)).
- Correlations across samples were averaged ([Schmidt & Hunter, 2015](#)). However, correlations are not additive and cannot be averaged. Average of sample correlations is different from correlation based on all samples.
- Dropping of one or more items of WIS distorts discriminating value of test ($Disc_T$) which is non-linearly related to theoretically defend test reliability ($r_{tt-theoretical}$), factorial validity and α_{PCA} both measured in terms of eigenvalues ([Chakrabarty, 2023b](#))

PROPOSED METHOD

Ordinal raw scores of i -th item (say 5-point) can be transformed to continuous, monotonic equidistant scores (E_i -scores) by taking positive weights $W_{i1}, W_{i2}, W_{i3}, W_{i4}, W_{i5}$ based on frequency of response-categories of an item so that $5W_{i5} - 4W_{i4} = 4W_{i4} - 3W_{i3} = 3W_{i3} - 2W_{i2} = 2W_{i2} - W_{i1} = \text{Constant}$, value of which is different for different items. Calculations of weights are based on following stages:

I. For i -th item, find maximum ($f_{i\max}$) and minimum frequency ($f_{i\min}$) of the response-categories. Take initial weights $\omega_{ij} = \frac{f_{ij}}{n}$.

Arrange the ω'_{ij} s so that

$$\omega_{i1} = \frac{f_{i\min}}{n} < \omega_{i2} < \omega_{i3} < \omega_{i4} < \omega_{i5} = \frac{f_{i\max}}{n}$$

II. Let intermediate weight $W_{i1} = \omega_{i1}$

Take common difference $\alpha = \frac{5f_{i\max} - f_{i\min}}{4n}$ since $W_{i1} + 4\alpha = 5W_{i5}$

Define other intermediate weights as:

$$W_{i2} = \frac{1}{2}(\omega_{i1} + \alpha); W_{i3} = \frac{1}{3}(\omega_{i1} + 2\alpha); W_{i4} = \frac{1}{4}(\omega_{i1} + 3\alpha) \text{ and } W_{i5} = \frac{1}{5}(\omega_{i1} + 4\alpha).$$

III. Consider the final weights $W_{ij(Final)} = \frac{W_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^5 W_j}$ so that $\sum W_{ij(Final)} = 1$ and

$$kW_{ik(Final)} - (k-1)W_{i(k-1)(Final)} = \text{Constant}.$$

Standardize E_i -scores to $Z_i = \frac{E_i - \bar{E}_i}{SD(E_i)} \sim N(0, 1)$ and further transformed to get proposed score P_i by $P_i = (100 - 1) \left[\frac{Z_i - \text{Min}Z_i}{\text{Max}Z_i - \text{Min}Z_i} \right] + 1$

where $1 \leq P_i \leq 100$ ensures uniformity in item score-range. Normally distributed P_i scores of items can be added to get scale score of i -th subject (WSI_i) also following normal distribution. If scores of the i -th item $\sim N(\mu_i, \sigma_i)$, $WSI_i \sim \text{normal}(\sum_i \mu_i, [\sum \sigma_i^2 + 2 \sum_{i \neq j} \text{Cov}(P_i, P_j)])$. Thus, probability density function (pdf) of WSI as convolution of item-wise normally distributed scores can be found where parameters of the distribution of WSI can be estimated from the data.

Properties:

WIS scores following normal consider pattern of responses unlike usual summative scores and give unique ranks to the individuals satisfying desired properties like:

- Same range of scores for each item. $1 \leq P_i \leq 100$
- Continuous and monotonically increasing. A marginal increase in score of an item will increase WIS .
- Avoid skew and outliers (so that there is no bias for advantaged or disadvantaged groups)
- For i -th item, contribution to WIS and elasticity are quantified respectively by $\frac{P_i}{WIS} \times 100$ and $\frac{\frac{\Delta WIS}{WIS}}{\frac{\Delta P_i}{P_i}}$ to show relative importance of the items.

Benefits:

- Provides total WIS -score of an individual irrespective of factor structures.
- Progress of the i -th person in t -th time-period over the previous year is assessed by $\frac{(WIS)_{i(t-1)} - (WIS)_{it}}{(WIS)_{i(t-1)}} \times 100$ which quantifies responsiveness of WIS and effectiveness of adopted policy measures.
- $(WIS)_{it} < (WIS)_{i(t-1)} \Rightarrow$ Progress in t -th period over $(t-1)$ -th period. Deterioration, if any, may be probed to identify the item(s) where deteriorations occurred and initiate possible corrective actions. Similarly, progress for a group of persons is indicated if $\overline{(WIS)_{it}} < \overline{(WIS)_{i(t-1)}}$
- Normality of WIS facilitates statistical tests of equality of mean and variance of WIS for two groups or a single group at different time periods like $H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$ or $H_0: \sigma_1^2 = \sigma_2^2$ using cross-sectional data or longitudinal data. Statistical tests of significance of progress of WIS can be tested by $H_0: \frac{(WIS)_{i(t-1)} - (WIS)_{it}}{(WIS)_{i(t-1)}} = 0$ since ratio of two normally distributed variables $\sim \chi^2$ distribution.
- Similar statistical hypothesis concerning WIS across demographic variables like gender, age, managerial positions, etc. can be tested by t -ratios or ANOVA.
- Estimation of \overline{WIS} and σ_{WIS}^2 at population level can be made from a representative sample.
- Different cut-off scores of different scales may be integrated by considering normally distributed WIS -scores and finding equivalent scores (x_0, y_0) of two scales by solving the equation $\int_{-\infty}^{x_0} f(x)dx = \int_{-\infty}^{y_0} g(y)dy$ for a given value of say x_0 i.e. area of the curve $f(x)$ for scale 1 up to x_0 = area of the curve $g(y)$ for scale 2 up to y_0 .

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- A group of individuals can be classified into four mutually exclusive classes in terms of *WIS*-scores with normal pdf $f(x)$ by quartile clustering with equal probability to each class i.e. $\int_0^{Q_1} f(x)dx = \int_{Q_1}^{Q_2} f(x)dx = \int_{Q_2}^{Q_3} f(x)dx = \int_{Q_3}^{Q_4} f(x)dx$

However, quartile clustering does not indicate efficiency of classification. Boundary points of classes should ensure that members within a class are similar (small within-group variance) and members between classes are dissimilar (high between-group variance). Efficiency of classification may be assessed by Davies-Bouldin Index (DBI) which considers ratio of within-cluster and between-cluster distances (Davies and Bouldin, 1979). For K -number of classes DBI is computed by

$$DBI_K = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K \sum_{j=1}^K (i \neq j) \text{Max} \left[\frac{\text{Diam}C_i - \text{Diam}C_j}{\|c_i - c_j\|} \right]$$

where diameter of i -th class $\text{Diam}C_i = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{x_i \in C_i} \|x_i - C_i\|^2}{n_i}}$

C_i : Centroid or mean of the i -th class; n_i : number of members in the i -th class.

Max. DBI = 1 and lower value \Rightarrow better efficiency.

The optimal number of clusters with lowest DBI value can be obtained from the plot of DBI and number of clusters.

- Method proposed by Chakrabarty et al. (2024) can be applied to find theoretical reliability (ratio of true score variance and observed score variance) as

$r_{tt(\text{Theoretical})} = 1 - \frac{2S_{Pg}^2(1-r_{gh})}{NS_p^2}$, where N denotes sample size; S_p^2 denotes sample variance; S_{Pg}^2 is variance of the g -th sub-test and r_{gh} is the correlation between the g -th and h -th sub-test (Split-half reliability). This involves dichotomization of the test in two parallel sub-tests say g -th and h -th. $r_{tt(\text{Theoretical})}$ avoids verification of assumptions of Cronbach's alpha.

- Validity of a multidimensional scale can be obtained as Factorial validity which is the ratio of the first eigenvalue to the sum of all eigenvalues to reflect validity of the of the main factor for which the test was developed (Parkerson et al. 2013). Factorial validity of *WIS* avoids selection of criterion scale with similar factor structure and administration of two scales.

- Possible to find extent of correlation between *WIS*-scores and factors contributing to workplace incivility like greater stress, overworked employees, an increased interpersonal misunderstandings, etc. and psychosocial factors of the working environment such as job insecurity, social support from co-workers, social support from supervisors, job demands and control (Torkelson et al.2016). The factors can be measured by appropriated methods or say by Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire (COPSOQ II) (Pejtersen et al., 2010).

- Impact of workplace incivility at the organizational level can be investigated by regressing *WIS* scores on decreased level of job satisfaction, impaired performance, lower productivity, less commitment to work, lack of loyalty to the organization, decreased satisfaction with managers and colleagues, a sense of injustice and conflict between work and family and increased absenteeism and turnover intentions. However, checking normality of error scores is needed in fitting such regression equations.

DISCUSSION

Proposed transformation of *WIS* scores (X_i) to normally distributed *WSI*- scores enabling meaningful arithmetic aggregation, satisfying desired properties, offers a number of benefits, including better measures of reliability and validity.

Normality of *WIS*-scores helps to undertake statistical test of hypothesis like $H_0: \mu_{WSI_t} = \mu_{WSI_{(t-1)}}$

or progress of *WIS* by $H_0: \frac{(WIS)_{i(t-1)} - (WIS)_{it}}{(WIS)_{i(t-1)}} = 0$, $H_0: r_{tt(\text{Theoretical})} = 1$ which is equivalent to $H_0: \sigma_X^2 = \sigma_T^2$ by F -test and also to

test whether two subtest scores are parallel by testing

$H_0: \overline{WIS}_g = \overline{WIS}_h$ by t -test and $H_0: \sigma_{WIS_g}^2 = \sigma_{WIS_h}^2$ by F -test.

Multiple regression of *WIS*-scores as the dependent variable can help to indicate relative importance of the factors leading to workplace incivility. Similarly, regression equation with impacts of workplace incivility as the set of independent variables and *WIS*-scores as the dependent variable can help to rank the impacts for an organization or for a sector like shipping, mining, health care, etc. However, checking normality of error scores is needed in fitting such regression equations.

Plotting of progress/deterioration of a sample of persons belonging to an organization across time helps to compare progress path that is, response to the policy measures for mitigation of workplace incivility from the beginning of the longitudinal study. A decreasing (negatively sloped) graph of WIS_t and time (t) indicates improvement over time and an increasing graph will indicate the reverse.

Responsiveness of *WIS* enables practitioners or researcher to know time-to-event outcomes from the beginning of observation (time of diagnosis) to the occurrence of the relevant events as a continuous variable.

CONCLUSIONS

The paper contributes in improving assessment of Workplace Incivility avoiding major limitations of and enabling parametric analysis for meaningful comparisons. Policy makers and researchers can take advantages of the proposed method of arithmetic aggregation of normally distributed variables to find relationship between supply side and demand side of WIS.

Empirical studies may be undertaken to investigate properties of WIS with emphasis on robustness and progress path of WIS.

Workplace incivility impacts the human resource of an organization. Accordingly, appropriate training and development programs may be developed to encourage positive personality traits like agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional stability, and openness to experience since people with those traits are less likely to engage in uncivil behaviors and to examine impact of such programs on possible decrease of absenteeism, increase of productivity, etc.

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